

Microscopic Polyangiitis, Revisiting ANCA-Associated Vasculitis: Case Report and Review

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ABSTRACT

Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) is a systemic autoimmune necrotizing vasculitis belonging to the group of antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). Characterized by pauci-immune crescentic glomerulonephritis without systemic involvement. AAV is an uncommon disease with an incidence of about 20 per million population per year in Europe and North America. The kidney is involved in more than 90% of MPA cases. Rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis is the most common clinical presentation or renal vasculitis, revealed by rapid deterioration of renal function, low-grade glomerular proteinuria, and constant microhematuria, with the presence of red blood cell casts in the urine sediment. Renal biopsy is the gold standard diagnostic test that confirms renal involvement of AAV. This report presents a case of a 23-year-old female with no pathologic history of any chronic disease, presented with acute kidney failure symptoms. Initial evaluation suggested rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis, but further diagnostic workup, including renal biopsy and auto-immune serology confirmed MPA. The patient was treated with glucocorticoids and Mycophenolate mofetil. Significant improvement was observed, with complete resolution and normal kidney function at the 3-month follow-up.

KEYWORDS: Microscopic polyangiitis, Rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis, (ANCA)-associated vasculitis, Nephritic syndrome.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) is a systemic autoimmune necrotizing vasculitis belonging to the group of antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA)-associated vasculitis (AAV). (5)

Characterized by pauci-immune crescentic glomerulonephritis without systemic involvement. (6) AAV is an uncommon disease with an incidence of about 20 per

million population per year in Europe and North America. There is a slight male preponderance. Incidence increases with age, with a peak in the 60- to 70-year age range. (3)

The pathogenic role of ANCA has been suggested by several clinical observations, reinforced by numerous laboratory findings, both in vitro and in vivo, confirmed by animal models of AAV. The almost constant positivity of anti-myeloperoxidase (MPO) antibodies in MPA patients and

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the close relationship between plasma levels of autoantibodies and clinical activity of vasculitis has transformed this test into a strong diagnostic tool. (5) It is unclear why autoantibodies to neutrophil self-antigens develop because both MPO and PR3 (proteinase 3) are sequestered from the immune system in primary granules, and following neutrophil degranulation at sites of tissue injury, are rapidly eliminated by specific inhibitors. Defective neutrophil apoptosis, or impaired clearance of apoptotic cell fragments, may lead to prolonged exposure of these antigens to the immune system. (3)

The clinical symptoms and signs of MPA may involve almost every organ of the body, similar to what can be observed in the other systemic vasculitis. Its clinical picture shares several features with granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA), but general signs, such as weight loss, low-grade fever, arthralgia, and myalgia, can be absent or quite mild. As a consequence of this insidious initial presentation, organs and particularly the kidneys, may harbor advanced lesions at MPA diagnosis. The most frequently affected organs in this disease are the kidneys and the lung, but the cutaneous and neurologic involvements are not rare. (5)

The current treatment of severe AAV involves two phases: Remission induction therapy based on the combination of glucocorticoids and another immunosuppressive agent, then once remission is achieved, maintenance therapy. Remission is usually achieved by a combination of high doses of glucocorticoids with cyclophosphamide or rituximab for 3-6 months. These agents can induce remission in more than 80% of patients. (6)

II. CASE REPORT

A 23 year-old female with only history of alcohol consumption since 18 years-old, and history of hip fracture due to a car accident at 10 years-old that require bone graft. About her gynecobstetric history she refers use of Levonorgestrel in multiple occasions, last dose was 2 weeks before the onset of the symptoms. She never has been pregnant or any history of abortions.

She begins 2 weeks before her hospital admission with persistent nausea and vomiting over 5 times a day, characterized by food remnants, she denied blood clots. Also refers hyporexia and fatigue.

At her initial evaluation she's found with elevated blood pressure, checking over 150/80 mmHg.

Physical examination revealed hematuria and peripheral edema. Biochemical exams revealed low grade anaemia (9.32 g/dL), and elevated serum Creatinine (3.8mg/dL) that give her an eTFG of 16 ml/min/1.73m², she had no serum electrolytes alteration. Urinalysis revealed proteinuria of 300 mg/dL, and erythrocytes 18-20 per hpf.

She was hospitalized with a presumptive diagnosis of nephritic syndrome. During her hospitalization Creatinine clearance (CrCl) was performed, with an CrCl of 17.04 ml/min, her urine output shifted between 2.4-0.95 ml/kg/hr.

Also, we performed autoimmune serology, finding an elevated levels of MPO-ANCA and normal value of PR3-ANCA, antibodies anti-DNA were completely normal.

A renal biopsy had been performed using PAS stain, showing mostly fibro-adipose tissue, extracapillary and endocapillary cellular proliferation and fibrinoid necrosis. The remaining material exhibit 30%-40% atrophy and fibrosis, the tubules show tubulitis, epithelial injury and protein resorption. There are several red blood casts. The interstium contains a moderate mononuclear inflammatory infiltrate in most of the material. The vasculature is within normal limits.

Figure 1. Renal biopsy with PAS stain showing mostly fibro-adipose tissue, extracapillary and endocapillary cellular proliferation and fibrinoid necrosis.

With this information we could integrate diagnosis of Microscopic polyangiitis (MPA), we start pulses of Metilprednisolone at doses of 1gr/day for 3 days, in combination with Mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) and Prednisone for remission induction. After treatment a posterior biochemical exam was performed, we observed serum Creatinine decreases and improvement of eTFG.

After stabilization and up-titration to maximal tolerated dosage, the patient was discharged with optimal medical therapy.

At the 3-month follow-up, biochemical exams showed an improvement of Creatinine clearance and urine output, with normal urinalysis. Clinically the patient was asymptomatic with total recovery pf her previous.

III. DISCUSSION

Diagnosing and treating promptly relapses can be challenging, as there are no good predictive or diagnostic markers. (1, 3)

Figure 2. Renal biopsy with PAS stain showing 30%-40% atrophy and fibrosis, the tubules show tubulitis, epithelial injury and protein resorption. There are several red blood casts. The interstitium contains a moderate mononuclear inflammatory infiltrate in most of the material. The vasculature is within normal limits.

The kidney is involved in more than 90% of MPA cases. Rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis is the most common clinical presentation or renal vasculitis, revealed by rapid deterioration of renal function, low-range glomerular proteinuria, and constant microhematuria, with the presence of red blood cell casts in the urine sediment. Renal biopsy is the gold standard diagnostic test that confirms renal involvement of AAV. Optic microscopy frequently reveals active necrotizing glomerulonephritis with crescentic extracapillary proliferation of parietal epithelial cells. These lesions can evolve into chronic and irreversible glomerular lesions, such as fibrotic crescents and segmental or global glomerulosclerosis. (4, 5, 6)

The actual classification of AAV-associated glomerular disease, proposed by the European Vasculitis Society (EUVAS) renal pathologists group, distinguishes four categories, depending on analysis of glomerular lesions. The focal class, characterized by >50% of normal glomeruli, has clearly the best renal prognosis followed by the crescentic class, defined by >50% of glomeruli with cellular crescents, the mixed class, and finally autothoes have confirmed the prognostic value of this simple and reproducible classification. (5, 7)

Management of AAV has evolved tremendously in the past two decades, with substantial improvements in survival and quality of life. Induction treatment is now well codified, but some major changes may again occur soon. There have been multiple randomized multicentric trials, such as PEXIVAS trial, RITUXVAS trial, or the CYCA-ZAREM trial; all of them with a long-term follow-up. It has been observed that Cyclophosphamide combined with glucocorticoids for 3-6 months induced remissions in 93% of patients. (6)

Mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) combined with glucocorticoids can be considered for remission induction in

patients with nonsevere MPA. This treatment was associated with a longer time to remission and less number of relapses at 18 months. (3, 6, 7)

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Many years have passed since the first descriptions of (ANCA)-associated vasculitides (AAV), usually found in autopsies with a difficult diagnosis in clinical practice. Since the 70's decade treatment with glucocorticoids has save many lives, but still, it has the remaining risk of relapses.

Our expanding knowledge of pathogenesis and genetic contribution has provided new therapeutic targets. Reducing the need for the cumulative use of glucocorticoids may become a reality with some of these newly developed treatments. The identification of reliable biological markers remains needed to better assess disease activity, predict disease relapse, and further personalize the treatment approach.

Many other questions of importance remaining to be answered include how to reduce the damage associated with the disease or its treatments and how to best treat nonvasculitic manifestations.

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